

1 **A fetal placental macrophage model of Listeria infection.**

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7 We studied Listeria infection in fetal macrophages by next-generation sequencing. We describe here
8 silencing of the clotting factor *F13a1* as a primary consequence of Listeria infection of undefined function.
9 Fetal macrophage produced *Il6*, *Il23a*, *Ccl7* and *Il1b* during infection with Listeria. Cells silenced surface
10 receptor *Mertk* in response to Listeria infection, as well as *Cd180*, but with induction of *Mfsd2a*. Listeria
11 infection in the fetal macrophage resulted in silencing of *Lynx1* and *Wdr91*. We describe activation of
12 microRNA miR-3945 in the fetal macrophage during infection with Listeria monocytogenes.

13 Citations

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